

Report of the 2nd Session of the Integrated Marine Debris Observing System Steering Committee (IMDOS-SC-2)

Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IO PAN), Sopot, Poland & online

19-20 March 2026

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Executive Summary

The 2nd Session of the Integrated Marine Debris Observing System Steering Committee (IMDOS-SC-2) took place on 19-20 March 2026 at the Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences (IO PAN) in Sopot, Poland. This hybrid event, sponsored by the EU-funded projects BioGeoSea and EU4OceanObs, successfully brought together global experts for a productive exchange that took IMDOS forward in coordinating marine debris observations worldwide. The two-day gathering was full of intense discussions in plenary and in breakout groups, taking IMDOS significantly closer to addressing the ambitious strategic objectives outlined in the 2023 IMDOS Strategy document.

Sixteen Steering Committee (SC) members travelled from around the world to attend the meeting in person, and four others demonstrated tremendous dedication by actively participating online from Australia, Asia and the Americas throughout the entire agenda. In addition, the Director and Deputy Director of IO PAN, as well as three members of the International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project (IOCCP) & GOOS Biogeochemistry Panel of Experts, attended the meeting in person as guests.

The meeting provided an excellent opportunity to check on the status of IMDOS Task Team activities and discuss gaps and needs for further action, which together informed the development of an action plan for the next 1-2 years.

Gaps in harmonization of observing methods and marine debris data dominated the discussions. This ultimately resulted in a clearer view of how IMDOS can make a difference by better coordinating the numerous activities in this space. To this end, the SC made decisions on how to best expand on the IMDOS community engagement, while capitalizing on growing coordination office capacity.

One of the immediate outcomes of the meeting will be the public review launch of the draft Marine Plastics Debris Essential Ocean Variable (EOV) Specification Sheet. The EOV development process is being closely monitored by the GOOS Biogeochemistry Panel, and is supported by a dedicated task of advancing marine plastics debris observation within the EU BioGeoSea project.

Ultimately, the meeting strengthened the idea that IMDOS can add value by acting as an inter-stakeholder broker when applied to observing approaches and initiatives, guideline landscapes, regional initiatives, and data systems. The meeting, therefore, positioned IMDOS less as a destination and more as a catalyst that can help move existing efforts into a more connected and usable international observing framework directly supporting the policy-making processes.

Meeting agenda overview

The meeting unfolded over two full days in a hybrid format, leveraging Zoom to connect in-person attendees at IO PAN with online participants worldwide. The event was designed to have a workshop format, fostering maximum interaction between participants and featuring several block sessions organized in breakout groups.

On Day 1 (Thursday, 19 March), the agenda began with a welcome address by IO PAN Director, Sławomir Sagan, which was followed by secretariat updates and a summary of IMDOS accomplishments in 2025. The agenda then proceeded with presentations and discussions on the IMDOS communications strategy, and overview presentations of all active IMDOS Task Teams. In the afternoon, the programme shifted to work on data harmonization in breakout sessions, concluding with open-floor discussions about the current capacity of IMDOS to address its strategic objectives.

Day 2 (Friday, 20 March) opened with guideline harmonization presentations and breakouts, then moved to Marine Plastics Debris EOV development, and included updates on planned major event participation, and wrapped up with action summaries and closing remarks. The full meeting agenda can be found in **Appendix 1**.

Meeting participants

The gathering drew Steering Committee members from the Sponsors & Advisory Sub-Committee and the Work Programme Sub-Committee, composed of Task Team co-chairs. Both IMDOS Co-Chairs, Amy Lusher (NIVA, Norway) and Alex Turra (Sao Paulo University, Brazil) were present at the meeting, as were the secretariat representatives from Mercator Ocean International and IO PAN. With over 20 in-person participants and sustained online engagement from participants attending from Australia, Asia, and the Americas. The hybrid model (available also for breakout sessions) ensured broad inclusivity. The full list of meeting participants can be found in Appendix 2.

Meeting objectives

The following core objectives guided all discussions during the IMDOS-SC-2 meeting:

- to strengthen IMDOS's mandate and positioning within the global marine debris observations landscape;
- to expand community engagement and impact through task team activities bolstered by the coordination office; and
- to develop a concrete 1-2 year action plan.

Building on these, the meeting reviewed progress made in 2025, refined communication strategies, mapped data harmonization initiatives, explored guideline promotion and gaps, advanced the development of the Marine Plastics Debris EOV, and prepared for major 2026-2027 events like [UNOC](#), [UN Ocean Decade](#), and [OceanObs'29](#).

Meeting proceedings

Introduction to IMDOS and 2025 accomplishments

IMDOS stands as a collaborative effort among the Group on Earth Observations (GEO) Blue Planet, the Global Ocean Observing System (GOOS), and the UN Environment Programme's Global Partnership on Marine Litter (GPML). The IMDOS SC continues to improve the consistency and clarity of messaging about the role of IMDOS both within the marine debris community and beyond, ensuring that the scope of its activities remains well aligned with its vision and mission. It is important to distinguish the coordinating function of IMDOS from the marine debris observing system per se, which is made up of a large number of participating organisations and individuals carrying out the actual marine debris observations or modelling efforts. Acting as a broker, IMDOS promotes the development and use of harmonized methods and sampling protocols, advocates for adherence to FAIR and CARE data principles, and advocates for an inclusive, truly global observing system.

Leading up to the IMDOS-SC-2 meeting, IMDOS had already achieved key milestones, such as forming the international steering committee, electing co-chairs, launching task teams with geographical diversity, holding five intercessional SC meetings in hybrid and in-person formats, and representing the initiative at international events. These accomplishments provided a strong foundation for the discussions in Sopot. Key accomplishments are listed below:

- Holding the inaugural meeting of the IMDOS Steering Committee (January 2025, Paris, France), which was established on the foundations of the previous interim IMDOS Steering Committee
- Appointing Amy Lusher (NIVA, Norway) and Alexander Turra (Uni São Paulo, Brazil) as IMDOS Co-Chairs
- Signing of the Declaration of Common Purpose by organizations comprising the IMDOS Sponsors & Advisory Committee during the 2025 UN Ocean Conference in Nice, France
- Convening the 2025 UN Ocean Conference Official Side-Event “Driving Change with Data: The Integrated Marine Debris Observing System”
- Establishment of the first Task Teams and convening their first meetings
- Participation in several community meetings and workshops (see imdos.org/news for details)
- Publication of workshop reports and peer-reviewed articles

Communications strategy and positioning of IMDOS

The first major substantive discussion concerned the IMDOS communication strategy. This session started from presenting the role of practical communication tools such as the website, social media, visual identity, and articles, but it quickly developed into a broader discussion about how to develop and communicate the identity of IMDOS. Participants emphasized that communication was not simply about visibility. It was also about communicating the mission of IMDOS in a way that was clear to scientists, data users, policy actors, and related initiatives.

One of the central discussion points was the IMDOS online directory. The group broadly supported continued development of the directory, but with important clarifications. The directory should not become another standalone database. Instead, it should function as a structured metadata catalogue and a visible map of initiatives, with strong connections to existing systems and a clear explanation of how it complements the [GPML's Global Plastics Hub](#). Participants stressed that the directory should make fragmented efforts visible, reveal the global footprint of marine litter observing activities, and help users understand where monitoring is happening, where gaps remain, and which methods or resources are associated with different initiatives. There was also support for categorizing entries by region and by type of activity. In particular, the discussion distinguished between long-term monitoring programmes and shorter-term research activities. That distinction was considered important because IMDOS is trying to support a sustained observing community rather than simply aggregate all projects without structure.

Participants also noted that the directory should help connect users to methods, training resources, and best-practice materials, making it a driver for information rather than only a list of institutions. These resources will be gradually made available to the community through the website, and in the future, their integration with the IMDOS Directory will be re-considered.

The website update was treated as a near-term priority, including the addition of Task Team landing pages, steering committee biographies, clearer navigation, and people-focused content.

The meeting also identified the need for a reusable IMDOS slide deck, stronger use of professional communication channels, and more systematic collection of community content such as events, papers, training opportunities, and job announcements.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Complete the update and upgrade of the IMDOS website, e.g. by building IMDOS Task Team pages
- Develop a universal IMDOS slide deck for use at meetings and conferences
- Set up a process to collect and publish community news (events, papers, training, jobs)
- Improve internal communication tools (SharePoint / document access and workflows)
- Further develop IMDOS online directory and clarify its complementarity with the [Global Plastics Hub](#)

Discussion on the role of IMDOS

Across both days, SC members spent significant time refining the language used to describe IMDOS. Participants recognized that the word “system” in the name can easily create confusion if it is interpreted as an operational, centralized observing network. For that reason, the discussion leaned toward explaining IMDOS as a community-led coordination mechanism, a broker between observing communities and data users, and a facilitator of comparability and visibility of data, knowledge and associated resources.

This discussion mattered because it shaped not only communications, but also the scope of work for the Task Teams and the kinds of deliverables that IMDOS should pursue. The group emphasized that IMDOS should not duplicate databases, impose rigid requirements on unrelated initiatives, or oversell technologies that are not mature enough for policy use. Instead, it should help create shared language, improve metadata, link initiatives, promote community-agreed best practices, identify gaps, and support pathways that allow diverse datasets to speak to one another.

Related to this, the meeting also examined the term “harmonization.” Several participants distinguished harmonization from formal standardization. The discussion suggested that formal standardization can imply an ISO-like endpoint that is neither realistic nor always desirable in a diverse and evolving field. By contrast, harmonization was described more as a process of making observations, metadata, protocols, terminology, and reporting pathways sufficiently aligned to enable comparability, interoperability, and fit-for-purpose use. This framing strongly influenced the action points for multiple Task Teams.

Task Team Overviews and way forward

The implementation of IMDOS Strategy is meant to be delivered through its Task Teams - modus operandi formally agreed during IMDOS-SC-1. Therefore, the Task Team session was one of the most detailed parts of the meeting. It allowed the SC to review where progress had already been made, where some groups remained at an early stage, and where IMDOS would need to prioritize effort to demonstrate value in the short term.

A broad conclusion from this session was that the task teams vary significantly in maturity. Some already have active expert communities (well-established outside of IMDOS), draft outputs, or concrete near-term products. Others still need a clearer scope, more members, and a sharper implementation strategy. The meeting did not treat this variation as a problem in itself, but it did lead to repeated calls for roadmaps, short implementation plans, and clearer statements of what each task team is trying to produce over the next 12 to 18 months.

Another major theme was the need to avoid fragmentation across task teams. Participants pointed out overlaps and interfaces among surface observations, remote sensing, modeling, indicators, harmonization, and data-for-policy work. As a result, several of the planned actions focus not only on outputs within a task team, but also on cross-cutting functions such as metadata alignment, shared terminology, pilot regions, and stronger communication between teams.

The role of the Secretariat was discussed not only as an administrative structure but as a practical enabler of the whole work plan. Besides finalizing the Terms of Reference and providing guidance for task-team modus operandi, the Secretariat will work with the Co-Chairs to determine where support, effort, and funding should be prioritized. This is important because many of the proposed actions listed below depend on stronger coordination capacity. With the appointment of a new member of IMDOS Secretariat, Kathryn Ortenzi (IOPAN, Poland), supported by the BioGeoSea project for the period April 2026-October 2027, there will be significantly more coordination and support for task team activities in this critical period of IMDOS implementation.

During the meeting, each task team delivered concise summaries of 2025 activities, if any, and/or presented plans forward, which are briefly discussed below.

UN Global Treaty

The UN Global Treaty Task Team, led by Thomas Maes (SEAMOHT LTD, UK) and Vitória Scrich (University of São Paulo, Brazil), urged a shift in how IMDOS positions itself towards Global Treaty development. Moving from a treaty-dependent posture to a treaty-enabling one recognizes that international policy processes are slow and that observing coordination cannot wait for a final treaty before acting. The SC applauded the Task Team for its approach to combine policy awareness with technical pragmatism, which would favour smaller regional building blocks and practical examples that could support future treaty implementation. Consequently, the following actions were listed on the Task Team agenda for the next 1-3 years.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Join the [INC informal and formal meetings](#), including potential preparation of a policy brief on the importance of marine debris monitoring
- Continue engagement with INC, UNEA and other global processes
- Ensure policy relevance of a minimum global monitoring framework (core indicators + methodologies) developed by the Development of Indicators and Monitoring System Design Task Teams
- Build partnerships and support (sub)regional harmonisation
- Select pilot countries and define needs and actions

Regional Observing Systems & Groups

The Regional Observing Systems & Groups Task Team, led by Mahesh Pradhan (COBSEA, Thailand) and Daoji Li (ECNU, China), remains in a conceptual stage of development. However, establishing global coordination based on existing regional structures and systems was perceived by the SC as one of the most promising ways for IMDOS to demonstrate value. It was noted that many Regional Seas already have substantial histories of work on plastics and marine litter, but that this work is unevenly distributed and often remains weakly connected across regions. Participants suggested that regional nodes could feed into broader IMDOS coordination while also drawing from it, making regional work a practical entry point for harmonization and community engagement. Establishing closer links with [GOOS Regional Alliances](#) is also recommended.

Based on the discussion led by Mahesh Pradhan, the group identified the following possible actions to be implemented in the near term.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Organize [a joint webinar with UNEP COBSEA](#) in June 2026
- Explore participation in [COBSEA side event](#) during the 11th [Our Ocean Conference](#) in Mombasa, Nairobi in June 2026.
- Explore participation in the 2026 SEA of Solutions event in conjunction with the [Asia Pacific Ocean Week](#),

- Establish stronger linkages with the [Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans](#) - 7 of the 18 Regional Seas Conventions and Action Plans are administered by UNEP.

Data for Policy Task Team

The Data for Policy Task Team, led by Georg Hanke (JRC, Italy) and Nao Takeuchi (UNEP GPML, Kenya), was described as being in an early phase, with its role still taking shape. The discussion highlighted the importance of understanding how monitoring outputs connect to policy-facing entities such as GPML custodians, national statistical systems, and regional reporting arrangements.

To this end, the task team would liaise very closely with the [UNEP GPML Plastic Monitoring and Assessment Harmonization Community of Practice \(CoP\)](#), and as a direct outcome of the meeting, three IMDOS SC members, Georg Hanke, Amy Lusher and Cherie Motti, were nominated to co-lead the “Plastics in the Environment” subteam of the CoP. The SC discussed utilizing planned CoP expert workshops to improve reporting of country data on marine plastics to GPML or other data portals, and identifying key performance indicators and harmonization areas for cumulative progress measurement. This work should start by understanding what receiving bodies actually need, which indicators are already being used, and where IMDOS can help bridge the gap between raw data and policy-relevant outputs.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Confirm the nomination of Georg Hanke, Amy Lusher and Cherie Motti as co-leads of the “Plastics in the Environment” subteam of the GPML Plastic Monitoring and Assessment Harmonization CoP.
- Attend the UNEP GPML and Nordic Council of Ministers workshop on “Unlocking Plastics Data Across the Lifecycle Through the Global Plastics Hub” and the GPML CoP Meeting for Workplan Finalization to be held in May 2026 in Oslo, Norway

Floating Microplastics Task Team

The Floating Marine Microplastics Task Team, led by Cheri Motti (AIMS, Australia) and Belén Alfonso (Kyushu University, Japan), highlighted its 2025 achievements, which include: formation of the task team with representation across 5 countries, definition of its scope, and development of the data value chain framework to map TT overlaps. Moreover, the Task Team identified core challenges for this domain, including lack of standardization, inconsistent quality assurance and quality control (QA/QC), limited platform uptake, and outlined the following immediate actions for the next 1-3 years.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Finalise the roadmap and definitions
- Establish expert network and registry
- Review existing guidelines
- Develop metadatabase of monitoring programs
- Refine harmonised surface sampling and laboratory protocols
- Deliver training materials

Seafloor Litter Task Team

The Seafloor Litter Task Team, led by Christopher Kim Pham (University of the Azores, Portugal) and Ryota Nakajima (JAMSTEC, Japan), presented their community accomplishments, in particular the recently published perspective paper ([Hanke et al., 2025](#)) which advocates for building a global observing system, with emphasis on harmonized guidelines, development of AI for image analysis, and the need for petabyte-scale data centers as well as adequate training. Moreover, it was noted that the seafloor macrolitter imagery expert community, stemming from the MSFD Technical Group on Marine Litter (TGML), has recently engaged new members across the globe (with a total of ~60 researchers), and has convened an online community meeting in December 2025. The task team has identified many challenges, most related to issues of fragmentation and lack of harmonisation across the broad range of environments studied. With clear consensus on the need to rely on imagery and observational data as opposed to trawl data, there remains the challenge of no alternative timeseries data available at the moment. The following near-term actions were proposed.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Convene an in-person workshop in April 2026, in Athens, Greece (successfully completed), building on the online meeting in December
- Publish a peer-review paper on best-practice guidelines for monitoring seafloor macrolitter using underwater observations and imaging technologies
- Ensure preservation of petabyte-scale data preservation through recognized data centre(s)

Development of Indicators Task Team

The Development of Indicators Task Team, led by Francois Galgani (retired, formerly at Ifremer, France) and Artur Palacz (IOPAN, Poland) was discussed in close connection with the Marine Plastics Debris EOV (see [section below](#)) and with wider policy needs. In essence, recommendations for what is currently feasible in terms of global observations will be summarized in the EOV Specification Sheet, while candidates for future indicators will be evaluated through the process being developed by the Task Team, also in close collaboration with UNEP GPML CoP work. In 2025, the core group of the Task Team was established, and a clear action plan was agreed. An initial version of the indicator evaluation template has been drafted, and the next steps are outlined below, along with milestones related to the EOV process.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Finalization of the indicator evaluation template and its distribution among an expanded group of task team members (second part of 2026)
- Finalization of the Marine Plastics Debris EOV Specification Sheet and distribution for public review (March-June 2026)
- Presentation of the Marine Plastics Debris EOV Spec Sheet for approval by the GOOS Steering Committee (September-October 2026)

- Development of an interactive Indicator Evaluation tool (1-2 years time scale)

Data Harmonization & Management Task Team

Data Harmonization & Management Task Team, led by Amy Lusher (NIVA, Norway) and Stefano Aliani (CNR, Italy), highlighted its accomplishments in 2025 which included the finalization of the report of the 1st international Data Harmonization Workshop held in Yokohama in 2023 (Palacz et al., 2025; currently embargoed for publication), meetings of the core group in the second half of 2025 and coordination with the Seafloor Task Team on drafting guidance for imaging and connecting to typology and AI based classification ([Hanke et al., 2025](#)).

In general, this Task Team provides fundamental support to several other Task Teams focused on various domains of marine litter, while at the same time requiring close collaboration with other thematic Task Teams, in particular the Design of Monitoring Systems.

The following actions were proposed on the 1-3 year time frame, with their successful realization strongly dependent on the amount of support from IMDOS Secretariat and availability of additional funding (e.g. through dedicated research projects targeting data harmonization).

ACTION ITEMS:

- Produce an IMDOS Technical Guidance Note on harmonizing monitoring workflows, in collaboration with the Design of Monitoring System Task Team
- Develop and refine TRL assessments for data quality, including links to harmonisation efforts and existing work (e.g., [EUROqCHARM](#), [Aliani et al., 2023](#)).
- Map and engage with existing initiatives and expert working groups engaged in harmonization activities (e.g. ICES, AMAP, PICES, SCOR, SCAR)
- Launch regional or targeted harmonisation support workshops and develop multilingual training resources to reduce barriers to interoperability and metadata compliance
- Develop a global minimum metadata schema and ontology for marine debris data in collaboration with UNEP, GOOS, GESAMP, and GEO Blue Planet

See [section below](#) for further discussion on this topic.

Beach Litter Task Team

The Beach Litter Task Team, led by Kostas Topouzelis (University of the Aegean, Greece), received substantial attention because it was recognized as both important and underdeveloped. Participants openly acknowledged that the team had not yet fully started and needed clearer organization, stronger membership, and a practical roadmap. The SC discussed how the team should be structured, which communities should be invited, what the geographical distribution should be, and how to identify capacity gaps at coastal scales.

The following actions were proposed during the meeting, building on some initial proposals from IMDOS-SC-1 in Paris.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Set up the task team and define clear objectives for the near- and long-term
- Publish and disseminate broadly the survey on shoreline monitoring methods designed by JRC (Hanke and Vlachogianni)
- Analyze the results of the survey to create a living document resource with existing methodologies and to map the beach litter observing community landscape prior to engaging them in harmonization activities
- Define a roadmap for inclusion of modern technologies (i.e. data collection, litter categories, reporting)

Design of Monitoring Systems Task Team

The Design of Monitoring Systems Task Team, led by Giuseppe Suaria (Italy) and Toste Tanhua (GEOMAR, Germany), was also seen as strategically important, but still at an early stage. Its goal will be to focus on providing recommendations on the design and evolution of a global marine debris observing system. The following actions were initially proposed to be executed in the near-term pending official task team formation.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Review existing marine debris monitoring programmes using a TRL and SWOT analysis approach to identify strengths, gaps, and priorities
- Develop a shortlist of mature monitoring methods suitable for implementation within an international observing framework
- Initiate statistical power and trend detection assessments to evaluate the effectiveness of existing monitoring programmes and identify optimal sampling strategies.

Remote Sensing Task Team

The Remote Sensing Task Team, led by Manuel Arias (Zenithal Blue Technologies, Spain) and Victor Martinez-Vicente (PML, UK), exists to liaise with the [IOCCG Task Force on Remote Sensing of Marine Litter and Debris](#). The group was represented at the meeting by Shungu Garaba (Uni Oldenburg, Germany). The discussion by the SC saw strong potential in drone imagery, ship-based cameras, and satellite observations to expand coverage and provide broad situational information. At the same time, the meeting emphasized that these technologies should not be oversold and should not be presented as replacements for in situ surveys, as those remain essential.

While there are published documents assessing the state of the art and maturity level of remote-sensing techniques for marine litter monitoring, participants proposed producing a simple guidance product that explains what remote sensing can do now, what it may soon be able to do, and what its limitations are. Example community reports on the topic motivated by discussion within the IOCCG Task Force on Remote Sensing of Marine Litter and Debris include ([GIZ, 2023](#); [Goddijn-Murphy et al., 2024](#)). They also suggested clearly separating

discussions on drones from broader remote-sensing topics, and ensuring that relevant guidance is visible on the IMDOS website and, where appropriate, linked into the Ocean Best Practices System. In effect, the task team was asked not only to advance methods, but also to act as a trusted interpreter of technological capability for the wider community.

Modeling Task Team

The Modeling Task Team, led by Atsuhiko Isobe (Kyushu University, Japan), was neither presented nor discussed during the meeting. However, based on the outcomes of IMDOS-SC-1 and discussions with other Task Teams it should be noted that coordination of modelling efforts could focus on supporting observing design, interpretation, and the development of usable information products.

Data Harmonization Initiatives

This session initially aimed to initiate a global mapping of data harmonization efforts, to examine which major initiatives are missing from the existing landscape map, where connections among initiatives are already present, and where IMDOS could realistically intervene. However, reflecting on the earlier discussions and lack of clarity among SC members on what data harmonization means for IMDOS and where the priority activities should be, the breakout session on data harmonization took the conceptual issues discussed earlier and turned them into more operational questions.

The discussions in groups, subsequently summarized in the plenary, showed that harmonization is indeed needed at multiple levels. It is needed in terminology, so that communities speak the same language. It is needed in metadata, so that observations can be interpreted and reused in line with FAIR and CARE principles. It is needed in sampling and analytical steps, so that trends and descriptors become comparable even if methods are not identical. And it is needed in reporting and data pathways, so that information can move from observing programmes toward broader data synthesis and policy use. In conclusion, the SC reinforced the message that the Data Harmonization Task Team sits at the centre of IMDOS's attempt to provide a practical "Rosetta stone" across observing communities.

The group pinpointed a few other known initiatives related to data harmonization such as the activities of SCAR, AMAP, SCOR, COST, GPML, ICES working groups ([SCAR Plastic Expert Group](#); [AMAP Litter and Microplastics Expert Group](#); [SCOR Working Group 174 SPASS](#); [COST ICPLASTIC](#); [ICES WG on Marine Litter](#); GESAMP WG40 & 43). Liaising and establishing stronger collaborations with those and other active groups was put high on the IMDOS agenda for the 2026-2027 time period.

Harmonizing Monitoring and Assessment Guidelines

The second day opened by revisiting the definition of IMDOS and the meaning of harmonization before moving into guideline-related presentations and breakout discussions. This structure reflected a deliberate attempt to connect conceptual clarity with technical action.

The plenary featured five presentations on key initiatives: floating macro litter via drones (stressing harmonized conditions), floating microplastics guidelines (cross-compartment alignment), seafloor litter imagery, beach litter protocols, and remote sensing technology. The presentation on the AMAP Arctic working group detailed phases, with Phase 3 (2026-2027) prioritizing assessments on monitoring litter and microplastics in water (micro), sediments (micro), shorelines (macro) and seabirds (fulmars); compiling data for QA/QC, intercomparability, and mapping; and policy integration via Heads of Delegation.

Subsequent breakouts grappled with IMDOS's role in the development vs. promotion of monitoring and assessment guidelines. This included questions about disseminating existing consensus guidelines globally, overcoming regional specificities, gauging training needs (workshops/webinars), and facilitating missing ones (e.g., biota ingestion, paint and other microlitter) through expert convening.

A central outcome of the morning was the shared view that IMDOS should help communities navigate existing guidelines rather than assume that it must write every guideline itself. This process will be facilitated through the new Marine Plastics Debris EOV and its implementation among the observing community. Participants pointed to many ongoing initiatives in different compartments and regions, including work on Arctic monitoring (AMAP LMEG), water-column microplastics (e.g. SCOR SPASS), seafloor imagery, and bioindicators. The challenge for IMDOS is therefore partly one of coordination: making these efforts visible, connecting them where useful, identifying gaps, and helping the community understand which guidance is mature enough for monitoring and which remains more research-oriented.

The action suggestions from this part of the meeting were concrete. They included organizing webinars on surface microplastics and sea-surface macro litter, publicizing and analyzing beach-litter surveys, adding drone and camera guidance to the website, deciding whether and how to engage more deeply with seafloor groups, connecting with new work on water-column microplastics (SCOR WG 174 “Small Plastics in the Ocean’s Interior: Coherent Analysis and Synthesis for better Scrutiny ([SPASS](#))), and promoting mature guidance through the community and the [Ocean Best Practices System](#). Participants also called for a short stocktake of existing guidelines and for deciding which phenomena should be prioritized in the near term.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Organize webinars on surface microplastics and sea-surface macro litter monitoring and assessment guidelines.
- Publicize the beach-litter survey on the use of monitoring protocols prepared by the Mediterranean Information Office for Environment, Culture and Sustainable Development (MIO-ECSDE) and JRC.
- Add guidance on the use of drones and fixed cameras to the IMDOS website.
- Decide whether, and how, IMDOS should engage more directly with existing seafloor monitoring groups.
- Connect IMDOS work on water-column microplastics with SCOR WG 174 “Small Plastics in the Ocean’s Interior: Coherent Analysis and Synthesis for better Scrutiny (SPASS).”

- Promote mature monitoring and harmonization guidance through the community and the Ocean Best Practices System.
- Carry out a short stocktake of existing monitoring guidelines across compartments and regions.
- Decide which phenomena (e.g. compartments, indicators) should be prioritized for near-term harmonization and guidance efforts.

Marine Plastics Debris EOV

The EOV session, led by Artur Palacz (IOPAN, Poland), focused on further development of the Marine Plastics Debris EOV Specification Sheet, as anticipated in the agenda. Here, the discussion was both technical and strategic. Maciej Telszewski (IOPAN, Poland), Director of the International Ocean Carbon Coordination Project (IOCCP) and GOOS Biogeochemistry Panel of Experts, emphasised how important the role of IMDOS as developers and future custodians of the proposed EOV is, in particular addressing the GOOS Strategic Objective #10 on “Humans impact on the ocean.” Maciej praised how the IMDOS community has managed to come together over the past few years to turn the original community vision into a concrete coordination mechanism and a backbone behind an evolving observing system capable of being integrated into the wider ocean observing system.

During subsequent work in breakout sessions, participants examined the current information provided in the draft Marine Plastics Debris EOV Specification Sheet divided among the three main sections: requirement setting, observing approaches, and data management. The committee used the EOV discussion to test how mature different strands of IMDOS work actually are.

The discussion also exposed where further work is still needed. Gaps related to water-column observations, biota indicators, and the prioritization of phenomena remain open. At the same time, the meeting showed that the EOV process can serve as a useful organizing framework because it forces the community to ask what is sufficiently mature, what metadata are required, as well as which products IMDOS is realistically able to support in the short term.

ACTION ITEMS:

- Collect any remaining steering committee comments on the draft EOV specification sheet by the end of April 2026.
- Prepare an updated EOV specification sheet incorporating these comments and release it for public review as required by the GOOS EOV adoption process.
- Coordinate the subsequent submission and review steps so that the Marine Plastics Debris EOV Specification Sheet can be considered for approval by the GOOS Steering Committee in the second half of 2026.

Summary of meeting outcomes

One of the clearest outcomes of the IMDOS-SC-2 meeting was greater convergence on the identity and mandate of IMDOS. The meeting moved decisively toward describing IMDOS as a coordination and facilitation mechanism that helps fragmented observations become more visible, more aligned, and more useful. This matters because a clearer definition will shape external communication, relationships with partner initiatives, and the scope of task-team outputs.

A second major outcome was the shift from broad ambition to prioritized implementation according to the [2023 IMDOS Strategy](#). The meeting did not reduce ambition, but it repeatedly emphasized lower-hanging fruits, short and practical outputs, and the need to concentrate resources where IMDOS can demonstrate value soon. Website updates, directory development, harmonization guidance, targeted webinars, publication of the Marine Plastics Debris EOV specification sheet, and more structured task-team roadmaps all emerged as examples of deliverables that can show progress within a realistic timeframe.

A third outcome was a more detailed action architecture for the task teams. Before the meeting, several task teams had broad mandates. During and after the meeting, those mandates were translated into more concrete next steps, such as expert meetings, inventories, guidance notes, surveys, webinars, pilot activities, and framework reviews.

Finally, the meeting strengthened the idea that IMDOS can add value by acting as a broker across communities when applied to observing approaches and initiatives, guideline landscapes, regional initiatives, and data systems. The meeting therefore, positioned IMDOS less as a destination and more as a catalyst that can help move existing efforts into a more connected and usable international observing framework, directly supporting the policy-making processes.

Consolidated actions after the meeting

Planned actions put forward and approved by the SC during the meeting essentially constitute the IMDOS implementation plan, which can be grouped into several categories of actions.

First, there is a **communication and visibility track**. This includes completing the website update through collection of SC bios, development of dedicated task-team pages, and the continued development of the IMDOS Directory of marine observing and monitoring programmes and initiatives, which provide the foundation for the actual observing system. In line with the professional visual identity resources, a universal slide deck for IMDOS SC will be designed to strengthen consistent messaging beyond IMDOS.

Second, there is a **harmonization and authoritative guidance track**. This includes the technical guidance note on harmonizing workflows, a stocktake of existing guidelines,

promotion of mature guidance through webinars and website resources, pilot regions or countries to demonstrate end-to-end harmonization, and continued refinement of shared language around harmonization and comparability.

Third, there is a **task-team development track**. This includes shoring up less mature teams, finalizing roadmaps and scopes, engaging additional experts, running specialist meetings, building registries and inventories, preparing practical outputs tailored to each domain, and fostering regular exchange and coordination across task teams to enhance knowledge-sharing, alignment, and collaboration.

Fourth, there is an **EOV and indicator track**. This covers completion of the indicator evaluation template, EOV specification-sheet revision and public review, possible development of an interactive evaluation tool, and stronger articulation of how indicators connect to observing practice and policy needs.

Fifth, there is a **regional and policy-engagement track**. This includes work with Regional Seas, participation in relevant events, closer dialogue with GPML Communities of Practice, support for subregional harmonization, and attention to how IMDOS outputs may contribute to treaty-relevant or SDG-relevant reporting environments.

Conclusions and perspectives

The IMDOS-SC-2 was not only a Steering Committee meeting in the formal sense described in the agenda. It was also a successful workshop in which IMDOS pursued turning a broad strategic vision into a more operational set of roles, priorities, and deliverables in line with the EU-funded BioGeoSea project, which includes a dedicated task to support IMDOS implementation. The process generated a substantial body of planned actions, particularly for the task teams, and many of those actions are detailed enough to guide work over the coming year and beyond.

It can be concluded that the meeting moved IMDOS closer to a practical coordination model. That model is based on clarity of role, selective prioritization, community-agreed best practices, and visible outputs that help fragmented observing efforts become better connected and more useful.

Acknowledgements

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Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. Additional travel support was granted to individual members of the IMDOS SC by their respective home institutions.

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Disclaimer

Otter AI was used to transcribe the audio recordings and to assist with language editing. Perplexity AI was used to support language editing of the report. All content was reviewed and edited by the authors.

Appendix 1: Meeting agenda

Integrated Marine Debris Observing System (IMDOS) Annual Steering Committee Meeting

Institute of Oceanology Polish Academy of Sciences, Sopot, Poland
19-20 March 2026

AGENDA

Objectives of the meeting

- Strengthen the mandate of IMDOS and its role and position in the marine debris observations landscape
- Expand the IMDOS community engagement and impact through activities of the IMDOS Task Teams supported by the coordination office
- Develop an action plan for the next 1-2 years

Hybrid format - Link:

<https://us06web.zoom.us/j/89557099264?pwd=Ovv1JuFoJgOncxgBgaz4Mlqs0Lnwjb.1>

Meeting sponsors

Day 1 - Thursday 19 March		
9.00-9.15	Welcome and meeting logistics	IOPAN
9.15-9.30	Presentation of the agenda and the organization of the 2-days	Artur
9.30-10.00	Updates from the IMDOS Secretariat <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Highlight the impacts of IMDOS in 2025 • Secretariat, resources 	Daphne
10.00-10.30	IMDOS communication strategy Presentation of the website, social media, visual ID, articles <i>How do we better engage the marine debris observing and modelling community to expand IMDOS participation and impact? What should the role of the IMDOS online directory be? How to best connect with the Global Plastic Hub?</i>	Artur
10.30-12.30	Overview of the IMDOS Task Teams <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Each task team will give a brief summary of their 2025 activities and/or the next steps envisaged. • Plenary discussion on the Task Team modus operandi, coordination and communication needs 	Alex
<i>Lunch Break</i>		
14.00-16.30	Towards coordination of Data harmonization initiatives <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Initiate a global mapping of known data harmonization initiatives • Ensure sufficient regional coverage • Discuss recommendations for IMDOS coordination – 4 parallel breakout groups (3 on site, 1 online) • Summary of breakout discussions in plenary <p><u>Guiding questions for breakout groups:</u> <i>Which major initiatives are missing from the mapping? What are the existing vs missing connections between them? What are the priorities for IMDOS to help better coordinate this space? What concrete actions are needed? What is the estimated timeline and resource needs?</i></p>	Amy and Stefano (TBC)
<i>Coffee Break [some time during the session]</i>		
16.30-17.30	IMDOS planning of cooperation / funding	Daphne
	Dinner hosted by IOPAN (place TBD)	

Day 2 - Friday 20 March		
9.00-11.00	<p>Towards harmonizing monitoring & assessment guidelines</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 5' presentations in plenary from key initiatives developing harmonized guidelines: microplastics / floating macroplastics / beach litter / seafloor litter / drones • Breakout group discussion on the needs for promotion of existing and development of new monitoring guidelines – 4 groups (3 on site, 1 online) <p><u>Guiding questions for breakout groups:</u> <i>How can IMDOS help disseminate and promote global adoption of existing guidelines?</i> <i>What are the main challenges (e.g. region specificities) hindering the adoption of the guidelines?</i> <i>Are training courses on these guidelines needed? Should IMDOS organize workshops or online webinars?</i> <i>What guidelines are missing? How can IMDOS facilitate their development (e.g. convene expert workshops)?</i></p>	Alex (TBC)
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
11.15-13.00	<p>Marine Plastics Debris EOVS Presentation of the Marine Plastics Debris EOVS, progress and way forward.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Further development of the Marine Plastics Debris EOVS Specification Sheet. Work in breakout groups (3 on site, 1 online) • Current version of the document will be provided ahead of the meeting. Groups will be asked to review and finalize sections on requirement setting, observing approaches and data management. • Plans for public review and presentation to the GOOS Steering Committee. 	Artur
<i>Lunch Break</i>		
14.30-16.00	<p>Events & Updates</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Prepare for major events foreseen for 2026 and beyond (UNOC, UN Decade) • Abstract + presentations • Towards OceanObs'29 	Daphne
<i>Coffee Break</i>		
16.15-16.45	Summary of actions & priorities for 2026	
16.45-17.00	Information on next in-person SC meeting, wrap-up and closing remarks	

Meeting sponsors

Appendix 2: List of meeting participants

IMDOS SC Members			
#	First Name LAST NAME	Affiliation	Attendance
1	Maria Belén ALFONSO	Kyushu University, Japan	Online
2	Stefano ALIANI	CNR-ISMAR, Italy	In person
3	Mafalda de FREITAS	University of Hawaii, USA	Online
4	Francois GALGANI	Ifremer & Echos d'Oceans, France	In person
5	Shungudzemwoyo GARABA	AWI & Uni Oldenburg, Germany	In person
6	Georg HANKE	European Commission Joint Research Centre	In person
7	Natalie HARMS	UNEP, Kenya	In person
8	Daphne LECELLIER	GEO Blue Planet, France	In person
9	Amy LUSHER	NIVA, Norway	In person
10	Thomas MAES	Seamoht Ltd, UK	In person
11	Cherie MOTTI	AIMS, Australia	Online
12	Ryota NAKAJIMA	JAMSTEC, Japan	In person
13	Artur PALACZ	IO PAN, Poland	In person
14	Christopher PHAM	University of the Azores, Portugal	In person
15	Mahesh PRADHAN	UNEP COBSEA, Thailand	In person
16	Vitória SCRICH	University of São Paulo, Brazil	Online
17	Giuseppe SUARIA	CNR-ISMAR, Italy	In person
18	Toste TANHUA	GEOMAR, Germany	In person

19	Konstantinos TOPOUZELIS	Uni Aegean, Greece	In person
20	Alexander TURRA	University of São Paulo, Brazil	In person
Invited guests			
21	Sławomir SAGAN	Director of IO PAN, Poland	In person
22	Monika KĘDRA	Deputy Director of IO PAN, Poland	In person
23	Maciej TELSZEWSKI	IOCCP Director, IO PAN, Poland	In person
24	Malek BELGACEM	IOCCP Project Officer, IO PAN, Poland	In person
25	Dominik KRZYMIŃSKI	IOCCP Communications Officer, IO PAN, Poland	In person
26	Kathryn ORTENZI	IO PAN, Poland	Online
IO PAN meeting support team			
27	Łukasz BARYSZ	IO PAN, Poland	In person
28	Emma KASZUBA-RAKOWSKA	University of Gdansk/ IO PAN, Poland	In person